

Bipartite entanglement through nonorthogonal pure states

M. Mansour¹

Department of physique, polydisciplinary faculty,
University Sultan Moulay Slimane,
Beni Mellal, Morocco

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the entanglement of a more general type of two qubits nonorthogonal pure state by using the linear entropy as a measure of the degree of bipartite entanglement. Moreover, we study the behaviour of this entanglement measure in the context of $Su(2)$ -coherent states theory and we reformulate it as a function of some new parameters that specify coherent states. Finally we find some conditions for maximal and minimal entanglement of nonorthogonal states in terms of the amplitudes of spin coherent states.

Keywords: nonorthogonal states, spin coherent states, bipartite entanglement, linear entropy.

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¹ email: m.mansour@usms.ma

1 Introduction

Quantum entanglement is one of the important ingredients in quantum mechanics, which has been discussed at the early years in [1, 2]. Recently, the quantum entanglement had been considered as a nonclassical resource for many applications of quantum information, communication and computations [3], where it is a key component in several ares of quantum information such as quantum teleportation [4, 5], quantum cryptography [6, 7], quantum dense coding [8, 9, 10] and quantum computation [3, 11, 12].

For quantifying the amount of entanglement, several entanglement measures have been proposed such as entanglement of formation [13, 14, 15], concurrence [16, 17, 18, 19, 20] and linear entropy [21, 22, 23], see reviews for more measures [24, 25, 26]. For the two-qubit case, the linear entropy which ranges from zero for a separable state to the value $\frac{1}{2}$ for a maximally entangled is a convenient measure of entanglement. The linear entropy is an approximation of the von Neumann entropy and is easier to calculate. The von Neumann entropy is considered as the standard measure of randomness of a statistical set described by a density operator.

One important concept investigated and widely used in the context of quantum information theory is the notion of coherent states. Coherent states were first introduced by Schrodinger [27] in the context of the harmonic oscillator. Later, the notion of coherence became very important in quantum optics due to Glauber [28]. The most important coherent states are entangled coherent states investigated in (see for instance [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 37, 35, 36, 38, 39] for more details). They found particularly a notable success in the context of quantum optics [40, 41, 42, 43, 44], quantum teleportation [45, 46] and quantum information processing [47, 48]. Spin coherent states introduced by Peremolov in [49, 50] and by Radcliffe in [51] are typical examples of entangled nonorthogonal states which describe several systems and also have some applications in quantum optics.

The aim of this paper is to study and measure the linear entropy of a more general bipartite entangled state constructed by linearly independent nonorthogonal states of the form $|\psi\rangle = u|\chi\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + v|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle + w|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + z|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle$. We formulate this entanglement measure in terms of the amplitudes of spin coherent states and find some conditions for minimal and maximal entanglement.

The organization of the paper is as follows. First, we review in the second section, the concept of linear entropy as a measure of entanglement of an arbitrary pure bipartite state. In the Section 3, we devote to investigate the entanglement of a more general type of two qubits nonorthogonal pure state. In section 4 we study the behavior of linear entropy as a function of amplitudes of spin coherent sates and find conditions for minimal and maximal entanglement. Section 5 contains some concluding

remarks.

2 Entanglement of an arbitrary pure bipartite state

A general pure normalized bipartite state of two qubits system is a vector in the tensor product $\mathbb{H}_1 \otimes \mathbb{H}_2$ of two Hilbert spaces $\mathbb{H}_1, \mathbb{H}_2$ for systems $\mathbb{A}_1, \mathbb{A}_2$, expanded upon the computational basis $\{|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle\}$ of $\mathbb{H}_1 \otimes \mathbb{H}_2$, as

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_{00}|00\rangle + \alpha_{01}|01\rangle + \alpha_{10}|10\rangle + \alpha_{11}|11\rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $(\alpha_{00}, \alpha_{01}, \alpha_{10}, \alpha_{11})$ are complex numbers satisfying the normalization condition

$$|\alpha_{00}|^2 + |\alpha_{10}|^2 + |\alpha_{01}|^2 + |\alpha_{11}|^2 = 1.$$

The amount of entanglement contained in the state given in (1) can be obtained by a direct analysis of the density operator $\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ of the system. A good measure of the degree of entanglement of a bipartite system ($A_1 \otimes A_2$) is based on the von Neumann entropy. The von Neumann entropy for any state (ρ) is given by

$$\mathcal{S}(\rho) = -\text{Tr}(\rho \text{Log}(\rho)) = -\sum_i \kappa_i \text{Log}(\kappa_i) \quad (2)$$

where κ_i are the eigenvalues of the density operator (ρ). The extreme values of the von Neumann entropy $\mathcal{S}(\rho)$ are zero for pure states and maximal for completely mixed states. To calculate the value of the von Neumann entropy, it is necessary to have the perfect knowledge of the eigenvalue spectrum the density operator (ρ). If we denote by ($\rho_1 = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{A}_2} |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$) the reduced density matrix given by the partial trace of ($|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$) with respect to the subsystem \mathbb{A}_2 and similarly for ($\rho_2 = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{A}_1} |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$), then the entropy of entanglement of the bipartite state $|\psi\rangle$ is defined as the von Neumann entropy of either of its reduced density matrices, that is,

$$E(|\psi\rangle) = -\text{Tr}(\rho_1 \text{Log}(\rho_1)) = -\text{Tr}(\rho_2 \text{Log}(\rho_2)) = -\sum_i \lambda_i \text{Log}(\lambda_i) \quad (3)$$

with the Schmidt coefficients λ_i are the eigenvalues of the density matrices ($\rho_i; i = 1, 2$). The measure $E(|\psi\rangle)$ is also known as the entanglement of formation.

In this work, we adopt the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle)$ as a measure of the degree of entanglement of the bipartite state $|\psi\rangle$. The linear entropy is an approximation of the von Neumann entropy and is generally a simpler quantity to calculate. This measure is based on the purity $\mathcal{P}(|\psi\rangle)$ of the state $|\psi\rangle$ (see [21, 22] and references quoted therein) and is given by the relation

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 1 - \text{Tr}(\rho_1^2) = 1 - \text{Tr}(\rho_2^2) = 1 - \sum_i \lambda_i^2 \quad (4)$$

It must be stressed that the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle)$ ranges from zero for $|\psi\rangle$ separable state to the value $\frac{1}{2}$ for a completely maximally entangled state.

3 Maximal Entanglement of bipartite nonorthogonal States

In this work, we consider the most general type of entangled bipartite normalized state, expressed by:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}}(u|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + v|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle + w|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + z|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle). \quad (5)$$

where $|\xi\rangle$ and $|\xi'\rangle$ are linearly independent normalized states, which span the two-dimensional Hilbert space \mathbb{H}_1 with $0 \leq |\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle| \leq 1$ and $|\eta\rangle$ and $|\eta'\rangle$ are linearly independent normalized states, which span the two-dimensional Hilbert space \mathbb{H}_2 with $0 \leq |\langle \eta, \eta' \rangle| \leq 1$. The normalization factor \mathcal{N} is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}^2 = & |u|^2 + u^*v\langle \eta|\eta'\rangle + u^*w\langle \xi|\xi'\rangle + u^*z\langle \xi|\xi'\rangle\langle \eta|\eta'\rangle + v^*u\langle \eta'\eta\rangle + |v|^2 + \\ & v^*w\langle \xi|\xi'\rangle\langle \eta'\eta\rangle + v^*z\langle \xi|\xi'\rangle + w^*u\langle \xi'\xi\rangle + w^*v\langle \xi'\xi\rangle\langle \eta|\eta'\rangle + |w|^2 + \\ & w^*z\langle \eta|\eta'\rangle + z^*u\langle \xi'\xi\rangle\langle \eta'\eta\rangle + z^*v\langle \xi'\xi\rangle + z^*w\langle \eta'\eta\rangle + |z|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

To investigate the degree of entanglement in the system involving partly nonorthogonal states, we apply the method developed in [30, 53]. Then we have to map the bipartite system into a pair of two logical qubits. For that end, one has to write the nonorthogonal states $|\xi\rangle$ and $|\xi'\rangle$ as a state of a logical qubit using the orthogonal basis $\{|0\rangle; |1\rangle\}$ of the two-dimensional Hilbert space \mathbb{H}_1

$$|1\rangle = |\xi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad |0\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}_1}(|\xi'\rangle - P_1|\xi\rangle) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

where $P_1 = \langle \xi, \xi' \rangle$ and $\mathcal{N}_1 = \sqrt{1 - |P_1|^2}$. And similarly we choose the two linearly independent nonorthogonal states $|\eta\rangle$ and $|\eta'\rangle$ spanning the two-dimensional Hilbert space \mathbb{H}_2 to be given by:

$$|\eta'\rangle = |1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad |\eta\rangle = \mathcal{N}_2|0\rangle + P_2|1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{N}_2 \\ P_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

where $P_2 = \langle \eta', \eta \rangle$ and $\mathcal{N}_2 = \sqrt{1 - |P_2|^2}$.

The bipartite entangled normalized state $|\psi\rangle$ can be written in the basis state $\{|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle\}$ of the tensor product $\mathbb{H}_1 \otimes \mathbb{H}_2$, as:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}}(w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|00\rangle + \mathcal{N}_1(z + wP_2)|01\rangle + \mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|10\rangle + \mathcal{M}|11\rangle) \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathcal{M} = (uP_2 + v + wP_1P_2 + zP_1)$$

which shows that the general entangled nonorthogonal state is considered as a state of two logical qubits. The normalization of the state $|\psi\rangle$ requires that:

$$|w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_1(z + wP_2)|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|^2 + |\mathcal{M}|^2 = \mathcal{N}^2. \quad (10)$$

The matrix density $\rho_{12} = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ associated to the entangled nonorthogonal state is given as follows:

$$\rho_{12} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}^2} \begin{pmatrix} |w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 & w\mathcal{N}_2|\mathcal{N}_1|^2(z^* + w^*P_2) & w\mathcal{N}_1|\mathcal{N}_2|^2(u^* + w^*P_1) & \mathcal{M}^*w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2 \\ c^*\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2(z + wP_2) & \mathcal{N}_1^2|(z + wP_2)|^2 & \mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2(z + wP_2)(u^* + w^*P_1) & \mathcal{N}_1(z + wP_2)\mathcal{M}^* \\ (u + wP_1)w^*\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2^2 & \mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)\mathcal{N}_1(z^* + w^*P_2^*) & |\mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|^2 & \mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)\mathcal{M}^* \\ w^*\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2 & w\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}_1(z^* + w^*P_2^*) & \mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}_2(u^* + w^*P_1^*) & |\mathcal{M}|^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

while, the reduced density matrix ($\rho_1 = Tr_{\mathbb{A}_2}|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$) is expressed by:

$$\rho_1 = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}^2} \begin{pmatrix} |w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + \mathcal{N}_1^2|(z + wP_2)|^2 & w\mathcal{N}_1|\mathcal{N}_2|^2(u^* + w^*P_1) + \mathcal{N}_1(z + wP_2)\mathcal{M}^* \\ (u + wP_1)c^*\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2^2 + w\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}_1(z^* + w^*P_2^*) & |\mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|^2 + |\mathcal{M}|^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

and similarly, the density matrix ($\rho_2 = Tr_{\mathbb{A}_1}|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$) is given by

$$\rho_2 = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}^2} \begin{pmatrix} |w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|^2 & w\mathcal{N}_2|\mathcal{N}_1|^2(z^* + w^*P_2) + \mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)\mathcal{M}^* \\ c^*\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2(z + wP_2) + \mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}_2(u^* + w^*P_1^*) & \mathcal{N}_1^2|(z + wP_2)|^2 + |\mathcal{M}|^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

It is easy, modulo some obvious algebra, to check that the positive eigenvalues of the matrix $\rho_1(\rho_2)$ are given by

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - 4 \left| \frac{uz - vw}{\mathcal{N}^2} \right|^2 |\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2} \quad (11)$$

Clearly, we have

$$\lambda_+ + \lambda_- = 1. \quad (12)$$

The entropy of entanglement for the bipartite entangled state (9) is given by

$$E(|\psi\rangle) = -\lambda_+ \log(\lambda_+) - \lambda_- \log(\lambda_-)$$

The linear entropy (\mathcal{L}) contained in the bipartite entangled state (9), can be cast in the following compact form:

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{(uz - vw)\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2}{\mathcal{N}^2} \right|^2. \quad (13)$$

It is simple to see that the state $|\psi\rangle$ given in (Eq. (9)) is factorizable (i.e., $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 0$) in either of the following situations: $|uz - vw| = 0$ or $\mathcal{N}_1 = 0(|\xi'\rangle = e^{i\phi_1}|\xi\rangle)$ or $\mathcal{N}_2 = 0(|\eta'\rangle = e^{i\phi_2}|\eta\rangle)$ and it is maximally entangled when $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$. The maximally entanglement of the state $|\psi\rangle$ ($\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$) is equivalent to the following condition :

$$\mathcal{N}^2 = 2 |uz - vw| |\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2| \quad (14)$$

The study and examination of the behavior of the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle$ expressed by the relation (13) will be done according to three different situations

1. **For orthogonal states :** $P_1 = \langle \xi, \xi' \rangle = 0$ and $P_2 = \langle \eta', \eta \rangle = 0$, the linear operator (13) reduces to:

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi \rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{(uz - vw)}{|u|^2 + |z|^2 + |v|^2 + |w|^2} \right|^2. \quad (15)$$

We notice now that the state $|\psi \rangle$ is a product state (i.e., $\mathcal{L} = 0$) if and only if: $|uz - vw| = 0$ and it is maximally entangled when

$$2|uz - vw| = (|u|^2 + |z|^2 + |v|^2 + |w|^2) \quad (16)$$

The last relation is verified when the components $\{u, v, w, z\}$ gratifies $\{u = z^*; v = -w^*\}$ or $\{u = -z^*; v = w^*\}$. In this situation the following orthogonal states are maximally entangled

$$|\phi_{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(|u|^2 + |v|^2)}} (u|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + v|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle \mp v^*|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle \pm u^*|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle) \quad (17)$$

2. **For partially orthogonal states:** $P_1 = \langle \xi, \xi' \rangle \neq 0$ and $P_2 = \langle \eta', \eta \rangle = 0$, the bipartite entangled state (9) reduces to

$$|\psi \rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} (w\mathcal{N}_1 |00\rangle + z\mathcal{N}_1 |01\rangle + (u + wP_1) |10\rangle + (v + zP_1) |11\rangle) \quad (18)$$

Then, the linear entropy (13) becomes

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi \rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{(uz - vw)\mathcal{N}_1}{|u|^2 + |z|^2 + |v|^2 + |w|^2 + u^*w\langle\xi|\xi'\rangle + v^*z\langle\xi|\xi'\rangle + w^*u\langle\xi'\|\xi\rangle + z^*v\langle\xi'\|\xi\rangle} \right|^2. \quad (19)$$

When the components $\{u, v, w, z\}$ gratifies: $z = u^*; w = -v^*$, the linear entropy (19), is obtained as:

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi \rangle) = \frac{1}{2} | (1 - |\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle|^2) | \quad (20)$$

which can reaches it's maximum value $\mathcal{L}(|\psi \rangle) = 1/2$, when $\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle = 0$. (see fig.1)

FIG. 1: The Linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle)$.

In the general case, the study of the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle)$ of the partly nonorthogonal state is done according to two different subcases:

- When the components $\{w, v\}$ gratifies: $w = 0$; $v = -zP_1$, the linear entropy (19), is obtained as:

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{(uz)\mathcal{N}_1}{u^2 + z^2\mathcal{N}_1^2} \right|^2 \quad (21)$$

Then the maximum of the entanglement measure $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$, is attained if we have

$$|u| = |z| \mathcal{N}_1$$

- When the components $\{z, u\}$ gratifies: $z = 0$; $u = -wP_1$, the linear entropy (19), can be rewritten as follows

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{(vw)\mathcal{N}_1}{v^2 + w^2\mathcal{N}_1^2} \right|^2 \quad (22)$$

Then the maximum of the entanglement measure $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$, is attained if we have

$$|v| = |w| \mathcal{N}_1$$

3. **For completely nonorthogonal states:** $P_1 = \langle \xi, \xi' \rangle \neq 0$ and $P_2 = \langle \eta', \eta \rangle \neq 0$, the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle)$ is obtained as:

$$\mathcal{L} = 2 \left| \frac{(uz - vw)\sqrt{(1 - \langle \xi, \xi' \rangle)^2}\sqrt{(1 - \langle \eta, \eta' \rangle)^2}}{|w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_1(z + wP_2)|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|^2 + |\mathcal{M}|^2} \right|^2 \quad (23)$$

The maximum of the entanglement measure $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$, is attained if we have the following equality

$$2 |(uz - vw)\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2| = |w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_1(z + wP_2)|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2(u + wP_1)|^2 + |\mathcal{M}|^2 \quad (24)$$

The study of the entanglement of the bipartite state $|\psi\rangle$ is done according to two distinct cases

- i) **In the first case, when the overlaps between spin coherent states are respectively given by** ($P_1 = -\frac{u}{w}$; $P_2 = -\frac{z}{w}$), the resulting entangled state is obtained as:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{|w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + |(v - wP_1P_2)|^2} (w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2 |00\rangle + (v - wP_1P_2) |11\rangle) \quad (25)$$

The linear entropy in this entangled pure bipartite system writes

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{|w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|(v - wP_1P_2)}{|w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|^2 + |(v - wP_1P_2)|^2} \right|^2 \quad (26)$$

In this case, it is simple to check that the maximality of entanglement is attained at

$$|w\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2| = |(v - wP_1P_2)|$$

- ii) **In the second case, when** $v = -uP_2 - wP_1P_2 - zP_1$, and we take for simplicity $w = 0$; the maximum of the entanglement measure $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$, is attained if we have the following equality

$$2 |uz\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2| = |\mathcal{N}_1z|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2u|^2 \quad (27)$$

The corresponding linear entropy, can be rewritten now as follows

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{|uz\mathcal{N}_1\mathcal{N}_2|}{|\mathcal{N}_1z|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2u|^2} \right|^2 \quad (28)$$

The maximum amount of this measure occurs for

$$|\mathcal{N}_1z| = |\mathcal{N}_2u|$$

which is the maximum entanglement condition for the state $(|\psi\rangle)$ given by

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_1z|^2 + |\mathcal{N}_2u|^2} (\mathcal{N}_1z |01\rangle + \mathcal{N}_2u |10\rangle) \quad (29)$$

4 Entanglement through spin coherent states

In the following, we use the linear entropy of the bipartite nonorthogonal state in the framework of spin-coherent states and we analyze its behavior in terms of the parameters that specify the coherent states. Let us first recall that a spin coherent state of the Klauder-Peremolov [49] can be expressed for a particle with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ (see [30], [31] and references quoted therein) as

$$|\xi\rangle = \frac{1}{(1+|\xi|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{n=0}^1 \binom{1}{n}^{\frac{1}{2}} \xi^n |n, \frac{1}{2}\rangle = \frac{1}{(1+|\xi|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} (|0, \frac{1}{2}\rangle + \xi |1, \frac{1}{2}\rangle) \quad (30)$$

The spin coherent states are introduced in [51] as the single-mode binomial states. Obviously spin coherent states coincides with logical qubits. Here and in the following $|\xi\rangle$ is short for the spin-1/2 coherent state $|\frac{1}{2}, \xi\rangle$ defined by

$$|\frac{1}{2}, \xi\rangle = \exp(\xi J_+ - \xi^* J_-) |\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}\rangle \quad (31)$$

where J_+ and J_- are the raising and lowering operators of the $su(2)$ Lie algebra and $\xi = \frac{\zeta}{|\zeta|} \tan(|\zeta|)$. The computational basis $\{|0\rangle \equiv |\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}\rangle; |1\rangle \equiv |\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\rangle\}$ span the two-dimensional Hilbert spaces \mathbb{H}_1 and \mathbb{H}_2 .

The more general entangled pure state of two-qubit system is given in terms spin coherent states as

$$|\Psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} (u|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + v|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle + w|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + z|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle) \quad (32)$$

where the four spin coherent states $\{|\xi\rangle, |\xi'\rangle, |\eta\rangle, |\eta'\rangle\}$ are expressed in view of Eq.(30) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} |\xi\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1+|\xi|^2)}} (|0\rangle + \xi|1\rangle) \\ |\xi'\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1+|\xi'|^2)}} (|0\rangle + \xi'|1\rangle) \\ |\eta\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1+|\eta|^2)}} (|0\rangle + \eta|1\rangle) \\ |\eta'\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1+|\eta'|^2)}} (|0\rangle + \eta'|1\rangle) \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

The overlaps between spin coherent states $\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle$ and $\langle \eta', \eta \rangle$ are obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle &= \frac{1 + \bar{\xi}\xi'}{\sqrt{(1 + |\xi|^2)(1 + |\xi'|^2)}} \\ \langle \eta', \eta \rangle &= \frac{1 + \bar{\eta}'\eta}{\sqrt{(1 + |\eta|^2)(1 + |\eta'|^2)}}\end{aligned}$$

Clearly, we have

$$0 \leq |\langle \xi | \xi' \rangle| \leq 1 \quad 0 \leq |\langle \eta | \eta' \rangle| \leq 1, \quad (34)$$

Using now equalities in Eq. (33) the state given in Eq (32) may be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}|\psi\rangle &= \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}}((\lambda + \gamma + \mu + \nu) |00\rangle + (\eta(\lambda + \mu) + \eta'(\gamma + \nu) |01\rangle + \\ &(\xi(\lambda + \gamma) + \xi'(\mu + \nu)) |10\rangle + (\xi\eta\lambda + \xi\eta'\gamma + \xi'\eta\mu + \xi'\eta'\nu) |11\rangle)\end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

with ;

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda &= \frac{u}{\sqrt{(1+|\xi|^2)(1+|\eta|^2)}} \\ \gamma &= \frac{v}{\sqrt{(1+|\xi|^2)(1+|\eta'|^2)}} \\ \mu &= \frac{w}{\sqrt{(1+|\xi'|^2)(1+|\eta|^2)}} \\ \nu &= \frac{z}{\sqrt{(1+|\xi'|^2)(1+|\eta'|^2)}}\end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The linear entropy given in Eq. (13) can be expressed and studied through these spin coherent states. It is given in terms of the amplitudes of spin coherent states as

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{2 |uz - vw|^2 \left| \frac{(\xi - \xi')}{\sqrt{(1+\xi^2)(1+(\xi')^2)}} \frac{(\eta - \eta')}{\sqrt{(1+\eta^2)(1+(\eta')^2)}} \right|}{|\mathcal{N}^4|}. \quad (37)$$

And in view of equalities (36), the linear entropy (37) becomes :

$$\mathcal{L} = 2 \left| \frac{\lambda\nu - \gamma\mu}{\mathcal{N}^2} (\xi - \xi') (\eta - \eta') \right|^2. \quad (38)$$

The minimum of the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 0$, is attained in either of the following situations: $\xi = \xi'$ or $\eta = \eta'$ or $\lambda\nu - \gamma\mu = 0$ or and its maximum is satisfied when $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$ which corresponds to maximally entangled states. To simplify our study let us assume that $\xi = \eta$ and $\xi' = \eta'$ and that ξ and ξ' are real amplitudes of coherent states. In this case, the normalized bipartite pure state $|\psi\rangle$ may be written as:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}}(u|\xi\rangle \otimes |\xi\rangle + v|\xi\rangle \otimes |\xi'\rangle + w|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\xi\rangle + z|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\xi'\rangle) \quad (39)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{N}^2 &= |u|^2 + |v|^2 + |z|^2 + |w|^2 + (u^*z + v^*w + w^*v + z^*u) \left(\frac{(1 + \xi\xi')^2}{(1 + |\xi|^2)(1 + |\xi'|^2)} \right) \\ &+ (u^*v + w^*z + z^*v + w^*u + v^*u + z^*w + v^*z + u^*w) \left(\frac{1 + \xi\xi'}{\sqrt{(1 + |\xi|^2)(1 + |\xi'|^2)}} \right)\end{aligned}$$

The linear entropy of the bipartite entangled state (39) is obtained now as

$$\mathcal{L} = 2 \left| \frac{\lambda\nu - \gamma\mu}{\mathcal{N}^2} (\xi - \xi')^2 \right|^2 = 2 \left| \frac{uz - vw}{(1 + \xi^2)(1 + (\xi')^2)\mathcal{N}^2} (\xi - \xi')^2 \right|^2. \quad (40)$$

To study the behavior of linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle)$ as a function of amplitudes of spin coherent states, we consider four distinct cases

case 1 in the first special case when $\xi' = \frac{-1}{\xi}$, we show by a straightforward calculus that

$$\mathcal{N}^2 = |u|^2 + |z|^2 + |v|^2 + |w|^2$$

then the linear entropy given in (Eq 40) reduces to

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{(uz - vw)}{|u|^2 + |z|^2 + |v|^2 + |w|^2} \right|^2. \quad (41)$$

The state $|\psi\rangle$ given is a separable state (i.e., $\mathcal{L} = 0$) if and only if: $|uz - vw| = 0$ and it is maximally entangled when $2|uz - vw| = (|u|^2 + |z|^2 + |v|^2 + |w|^2)$. The maximum value of the linear entropy is given when the components $\{u, v, w, z\}$ gratifies $\{z = u^*; w = -v^*\}$ or $\{z = -u^*; w = v^*\}$

case 2 In the second case when $\xi' = 0$, we take $z = u = 0, v = \cos(\theta), w = \sin(\theta)$, the entangled bipartite state (39) turns to a superposition obtained by mixing the vacuum state and a $su(2)$ coherent state examined in [52, 54, 55]

$$|\psi_0\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} (\cos\theta|\xi\rangle \otimes |0\rangle + \sin\theta|0\rangle \otimes |\xi\rangle) \quad (42)$$

with the overlap $\langle \xi, 0 \rangle$ is given by

$$\langle \xi, 0 \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1 + \xi^2)}}$$

and the normalization factor \mathcal{N}

$$\mathcal{N}^2 = 2 + (2\sin(\theta)\cos(\theta))\left(\frac{1}{(1 + |\xi|^2)}\right)$$

It is remarkable to stress that the entangled bipartite states (42) share equivalent properties with the so-called NOON states investigated in ([54, 56, 57]).

The linear entropy of the bipartite entangled state (42) can be written as :

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi_0\rangle) = 2 \left| \frac{\sin\theta\cos\theta}{(1 + \xi^2)(2 + 2\sin\theta\cos\theta(\frac{1}{(1 + |\xi|^2))})} (\xi)^2 \right|^2. \quad (43)$$

and if we set the real parameter θ to its values at the extremum of the linear entropy $\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}(|\psi_0\rangle)}{\partial\theta} = 0$. This corresponds to $\theta = \frac{\pi}{4}$, the linear entropy is then given by

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi_0\rangle) = 2\left(\frac{\xi^2}{2 + \xi^2}\right)^2. \quad (44)$$

The linear entropy reaches the maximum $\mathcal{L}(|\psi_0\rangle) = 1/2$ when the amplitude (ξ) of the spin coherent state $|\xi\rangle$ is sufficiently large (see Fig 2).

FIG. 2: The Linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(\xi)$.

case 3 For the third case we consider the complex coefficients given as follows

$$u = 0; \quad v = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}; \quad w = \frac{-i}{\sqrt{2}}; \quad z = 0$$

The state (39) reduces now to the state expressed as:

$$|\psi_3\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \left(\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} |\xi\rangle \otimes |\xi'\rangle + \frac{-i}{\sqrt{2}} |\xi'\rangle \otimes |\xi\rangle \right) \quad (45)$$

with

$$\mathcal{N}^2 = \frac{(\xi - \xi')^2}{(1 + \xi^2)(1 + (\xi')^2)}$$

The linear entropy of this state ($|\psi_1\rangle$) is given by

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi_1\rangle) = \frac{1}{2} \left| \frac{(\xi - \xi')^2}{2 + \xi^2 + (\xi')^2 + 2\xi\xi' + 2\xi^2(\xi')^2} \right|^2 \quad (46)$$

The maximum of the linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(|\psi_1\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$ corresponds to the case when the two states $|\xi\rangle$ and $|\xi'\rangle$ are orthogonal $\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle = 0$ (see Fig.3)

case 4 For the latter case we consider the complex coefficients in Eq (32) given as follows

$$u = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}; \quad v = 0; \quad w = 0; \quad z = \frac{-i}{\sqrt{2}}$$

The state (39) reduces now to the state expressed as follows:

$$|\psi_2\rangle = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \left(\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} |\xi\rangle \otimes |\xi\rangle + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} |\xi'\rangle \otimes |\xi'\rangle \right) \quad (47)$$

Similarly to the third case, the amount of entanglement contained in the bipartite entangled state (47) is given by :

$$\mathcal{L}(|\psi_2\rangle) = \frac{1}{2} \left| \frac{(\xi - \xi')^2}{2 + \xi^2 + (\xi')^2 + 2\xi\xi' + 2\xi^2(\xi')^2} \right|^2 \quad (48)$$

The maximum of the linear entropy ($\mathcal{L}(|\psi_2\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}$) corresponds to the case when the two states $|\xi\rangle$ and $|\xi'\rangle$ are orthogonal $\langle \xi, \xi' \rangle = 0$. (see Fig.3).

FIG.3: The Linear entropy $\mathcal{L}(\xi, \xi')$.

5 Conclusion

we have studied the entanglement of the more general type of two-qubit nonorthogonal pure states of the form $|\psi\rangle = u|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + v|\xi\rangle \otimes |\eta'_i\rangle + w|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta\rangle + z|\xi'\rangle \otimes |\eta'\rangle$, constructed by linearly independent spin coherent states. We have used the linear entropy as a measure of entanglement and we have expressed it in terms the amplitudes of $su(2)$ coherent states. We have given also some conditions for the minimal and maximal of entanglement in the case of two-qubit general pure states. The case of mixed nonorthogonal states is examined in [39]. The physical importance of entangled coherent states lies in the fact that they are experimentally easy to generate, and they can extensively be used in quantum information tasks. For example, two entangled coherent states are used to realize an effective quantum computation[47, 58] and quantum teleportation. The bipartite nonorthogonal coherent states are expected to have more application in quantum computation and quantum information. We intend to generalise this work to the case of multipartite system in a forthcoming paper and examine possible applications to the field of quantum optics.

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